

QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Quantum cryptography uses quantum mechanics to guarantee secure communication. It enables two parties to produce a shared random bit string known only to them, which can be used as a key to encrypt and decrypt messages.

An important and unique property of quantum cryptography is the ability of the two communicating users to detect the presence of any third party trying to gain knowledge of the key. This results from a fundamental part of quantum mechanics: the process of measuring a quantum system in general disturbs the system.

A third party trying to eavesdrop on the key must in some way measure it, thus introducing detectable anomalies. By using quantum superposition or quantum entanglement and transmitting information in quantum states, a communication system can be implemented which detects eavesdropping. If the level of eavesdropping is below a certain threshold a key can be produced which is guaranteed as secure, otherwise no secure key is possible and communication is aborted.

The security of quantum cryptography relies on the foundations of quantum mechanics, in contrast to traditional public key cryptography which relies on the computational difficulty of certain mathematical functions, and cannot provide any indication of eavesdropping or guarantee of key security.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background

Quantum cryptography is the science of exploiting quantum mechanical properties to perform cryptographic tasks. Quantum cryptography is derived from two words quantum (/ˈkwɒntəm/) and cryptography (krɪpˈtɒgrəfi). Quantum can be defined as a discrete quantity of energy proportional in magnitude to the frequency of the radiation it represents. While cryptography is the process of converting ordinary information (called plaintext) into unintelligible text (called cipher-text) with the help of a key. This concept is best described by explaining quantum computing and data cryptography.

Quantum computing is based on a new kind of data unit that could be called non-binary (neither 0 nor 1), as it has more than two possible values. A traditional computer works on bits of data that are binary, or Boolean, with only two possible values: 0 or 1. In contrast, a quantum bit, or "qubit," has possible values of 1, 0 or a superposition of 1 and 0, in the case of an unknown value.

According to scientists, qubits are based on physical atoms and molecular structures. However, many find it helpful to theorize a qubit as a binary data unit with superposition. The use of qubits makes the practical quantum computer model quite difficult. Traditional hardware requires altering to read and use these unknown values

Another idea, known as entanglement, uses quantum theory to suggest that accurate values cannot be obtained in the ways that traditional computers read binary bits. It also has been suggested that a quantum computer is based on a non-deterministic model, where the computer has more than one possible outcome for any given case or situation. Each of these ideas provides a foundation for the theory of actual quantum computing.

Cryptography on the other hand is the art of hidden a clear data. The word was derived from ancient Greeks: kryptos "hidden secret" and graphein "to write". It is the practice and study of techniques for secure communication in the presence of third parties called adversaries. More generally, cryptography is about constructing and analysing protocols that prevent third parties or the public from reading private messages; various aspects in information security such as data confidentiality, data integrity, authentication, and non-repudiation are central to modern cryptography (Wikipedia, 2018).

The first military application of cryptography came in the fifth century BC and was invented by the Spartans of Greece. Their system involved wrapping a strip of leather around a staff (known as a skytale), writing the message lengthways along the staff and then removing the leather. The markings on the leather were then unintelligible to anyone without a matching staff. In a sense the skytale could be said to be the first cryptographic key, as the only people who could read the message were those who possessed a staff of exactly the same diameter as the one used to encipher the message.

Then, as now, the primary motivating factor behind cryptography development and research has been to keep military communications from the enemy. Julius Caesar used an early substitution cipher, which now bears his name, for communication with his generals. The Caesar cipher used a shift of three places along in the alphabet to convert a plaintext letter to a cipher-text one, so A enciphered to D, B to E and so on.

1.1 Definition of Terms

Qubit: also referred to as *quantum bit* is the basic unit of quantum information — the quantum version of the classical binary bit (i.e. 0 or 1) physically realized with a two-state device

Cipher: is a system of writing that prevents third party from accessing the true interpretation of a message. It is a secretive or disguised way of writing.

Communication: is a process of simply sending a message through a systemic medium that is understood by both the sender and receiver of the message.

Plaintext and Cipher-text: are typically opposites of each other. Plaintext is any information before it has been encrypted. Cipher-text is the output information of an encryption cipher.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 The Evolution of Cryptography

The earliest known information containing components of cryptography originates in the Egyptian town Menet Khufu on the tomb of nobleman Khnumhotep II nearly 4,000 years ago. In about 1900 B.C. Khnumhotep's scribe drew his master's life in his tomb. As he drew the hieroglyphics he used a number of unusual symbols to obscure the meaning of the inscriptions (Nicholas G. McDonald et al, 2013).

This method of encryption is an example of a **substitution cipher**, which is any cipher system which substitutes one symbol or character for another. The timelines below depicts the evolution of cryptography from classical cryptography to modern cryptographic systems.

2.1 Hieroglyphs

This is a stylized picture of an object representing a word, syllable, or sound, as found in ancient Egyptian and certain other writing systems. They were formal writing system achieved by combining logographic, syllabic and alphabetic elements, with a total of some 1,000 distinct characters (see sample below).

Fig 1. Sample Hieroglyphs taken from Khnumhotep II

As the Egyptian culture evolved, hieroglyphic writings became more common. One of the shortcomings of this method of encryption was relatively easy to break for those who could read and write (i.e. decryption becomes general).

2.2 Scytale

The first recorded use of cryptography for correspondence was by the Spartans, who as early as 400 BC employed a cipher device called the scytale for secret communication between military commanders. The scytale consisted of a tapered baton, around which was spirally wrapped a strip of parchment or leather on which the message was then written.

When unwrapped, the letters were scrambled in order and formed the cipher; however, when the strip was wrapped around another baton of identical proportions to the original, the plaintext reappeared. Thus, the Greeks were the inventors of the first **transposition cipher**.

Fig 2. Spartan's Scytale sample

A transposition cipher, which is any cipher system that changes the order of the characters rather than changing the characters themselves. In today's standards, the Scytale would be very easy to decipher

2.3 Caesar's Cipher – Substitution Method

About 2,000 years ago, Caesar, being commander of the Roman army, solved the problem of secure communication using the substitution encryption method. Caesar developed a substitution cipher method in which he would substitute letters for different letters. Only those who knew the substitution used could decipher the secret messages.

Now when the messengers were overtaken the secret messages were encrypted and not exposed. The figure below shows a sample Caesar's Cipher

Fig 3. Substitution Cipher Method

Using the figure3 above, the following narration can be created

Original Message: *The Enemies are One Hundred*

Encrypted message: *Fac Cdcgrcb ksc Mdc Ahdjscj*

A randomized order of substitution yields a much larger amount of security due to the larger amount of possible orderings.

Note: *Keyword = LEMON (12, 5, 13, 15, 14)*

2.4 Alberti-Vigenere Cipher

The Leon Battista Alberti encryption system is the base concept of a poly alphabetic cipher, which switches through several substitution ciphers throughout encryption. This concept was then used to develop the **Alberti-Vigenere Cipher** system pictured below:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z
A	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z
B	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A
C	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B
D	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C
E	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D
F	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E
G	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F
H	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
I	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
J	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
K	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
L	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
M	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
N	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
O	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
P	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
Q	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
R	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
S	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
T	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S
U	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
V	V	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U
W	W	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V
X	X	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W
Y	Y	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X
Z	Z	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y

Fig4: Alberti-Vigenere Square Cipher

The Blaise Vigenere Cipher works exactly like the Caesar except that it changes the key throughout the encryption process.

The Vigenere Cipher uses a grid of letters that give the method of substitution. This grid is called a Vigenere Square or a Vigenere Table. The grid is made up of 26 alphabets offset from each other by one letter.

Using the Alberti-Vigenere Cipher above the follow message can be encrypted as shown below:

Plaintext: ATTACKATDAWN
Keyword: **LEMON LEMON LE** **(LEMON = 12, 5, 14, 15, 13)**
Cipher-text: LXFOPVEFRNHR

These cryptography systems and more explains the several encryption techniques adopted in the ancient days. This were otherwise referred to as classical cryptography

2.5 Modern Encryption Techniques

In our Information Age, the need for protecting information is more pronounced than ever. Secure communication for the sensitive information is not only compelling for military or government institutions but also for the business sector and private individuals. The exchange of sensitive information over wired and/or wireless Internet, such as bank transactions, credit card numbers and telecommunication services are already common practices.

As the world becomes more connected, the dependency on electronic services has become more pronounced. In order to protect valuable data (i.e. security services) in computer and communication systems from unauthorized disclosure and modification, reliable and non-interceptable means for data storage and transmission must be adopted.

These security services deploys mathematical techniques related to Information security such as providing confidentiality, data integrity, authentication and non-repudiation.

2.6 Symmetric Crypto-system

Mathematically, a symmetric key cryptosystem can be defined as the tuple (P, C, K, E, D) where:

P represents the set of finitely many possible plain-texts, C represents the set of finitely many possible cipher-texts, K represents the key space, i.e., the set of finitely many possible keys, E represents the encryption rule and D represents the decryption rule.

It is sometimes called *secret-key cryptography* in which the sender and receiver of a message share a single, common key that is used to encrypt and decrypt the message.

Fig 5: Symmetric Cryptography

So an encryption process, given a plaintext (P), a key (K) gives the cipher-text (C). Thus: $E(P, K) = C$.

A decryption process is the exact opposite, given cipher-text and the key gives the original plaintext. Thus: $D(C, K) = P$.

Also this means that the process is reversible so: $D(E(K, P), K) = P$

2.7 Asymmetric Crypto-system

Asymmetric cryptography, also known as public key cryptography, uses public and private keys to encrypt and decrypt data. The keys are simply large numbers that have been paired together but are not identical (asymmetric).

One key in the pair can be shared with everyone; it is called the *public key*. The other key in the pair is kept secret; it is called the *private key*. Either of the keys can be used to encrypt a message; the opposite key from the one used to encrypt the message is used for decryption.

Fig 6: Asymmetric (Public Key) Cryptography

2.8 Difference Between Symmetric and Asymmetric Encryption

The difference between the symmetric and asymmetric encryption methodologies are listed in the table below:

	Symmetric Encryption	Asymmetric Encryption
1	It uses a single key that needs to be shared among the people who need to receive the message	It uses a pair of public key and a private key to encrypt and decrypt messages when communicating.
2	Symmetric encryption is an old technique	Asymmetric encryption is relatively new.
3	Enable Key Sharing methodology	Eliminate the need to share the key by using a pair of public-private keys
4	It is faster	It takes relatively more time

2.9 Cryptographic Hash Function

A cryptographic hash function is an algorithm that can be run on a data such as an individual file or a password to produce a value called a checksum. The main use of a cryptographic hash function is to verify the authenticity of a piece of data. Two files can be assumed to be identical only if the checksums generated from each file, using the same cryptographic hash function, are identical.

Some commonly used cryptographic hash functions include MD5 (Message Digest Algorithm – 5) and SHA-1 (Secured Hash Algorithm – 1), although many others also exist.

INPUT	HASH
Hi	3639EFC08A8B273B1619E82E78C29A7DF02C1051B1820E99FC395DCAA3326B8
Welcome to Unilag	53A53FC9E2A03F9B6E66D84BA701574CD9CF5F01FB498C41731881BCDC68A7C8

Fig 7: Sample Hash Conversion using SHA-1

2.10 Passwords and Cryptographic Hash Functions

A database saves user passwords in a manner similar to a rainbow table. When a password is entered, the checksum is generated and compared with the encrypted record with your username. User is then granted access if the two are identical.

Given that a cryptographic hash function produces a non-reversible checksum, is it safe for a user to make the password as simple as 12345, instead of 12@34\$5, simply because the checksums themselves can't be understood? No, and here's why.

These two passwords are both impossible to decipher just by looking just at the checksums:

MD5 for 12345: `827ccb0eea8a706c4c34a16891f84e7b`

MD5 for 12@34\$5: `a4d3cc004f487b18b2ccd4853053818b`

	id	login	email	password
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit <input type="checkbox"/> Copy <input type="checkbox"/> Delete	1	Tester	itsjustanotheremail@mail.com	cdb662ff7eaa975e2990760b1a5c0834
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit <input type="checkbox"/> Copy <input type="checkbox"/> Delete	2	Tester2	tester@mail.com	b5500dfb568d36e779c64846004d3b76
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit <input type="checkbox"/> Copy <input type="checkbox"/> Delete	3	Tester3	tester3@mail.com	48503dfd58720bd5ff35c102065a52d7
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit <input type="checkbox"/> Copy <input type="checkbox"/> Delete	4	Admin	tester4admin@mail.com	2e33a9b0b06aa0a01ede70995674ee23

Fig 8: Sample SQL Database using the Hash Algorithm to store users password

2.11 RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman) Crypto-system

RSA is a cryptosystem for public-key encryption, and is widely used for securing sensitive data, particularly when being sent over an insecure network such as the Internet. It was first described in 1977 by Ron Rivest, Adi Shamir and Leonard Adleman of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Public-key cryptography, also known as asymmetric cryptography (as explained above), uses two different but mathematically linked keys, one public and one private.

The public key can be shared with everyone, whereas the private key must be kept secret. In RSA cryptography, both the public and the private keys can encrypt a message; the opposite key from the one used to encrypt a message is used to decrypt it. This attribute is one reason why RSA has become the most widely used asymmetric algorithm: It provides a method of assuring the confidentiality, integrity, authenticity and non-reputability of electronic communications and data storage.

Fig9: Diagram showing how RSA Encryption Works

The client and the server in Transport Layer Security (TLS) Handshake Protocol authenticate each other using certificates or pre-shared keys (PSK), instantiate the negotiation of security parameters and compute the session key that is used to encrypt exchanged data. The simple table below shows how to encrypt/decrypt a message using the RSA algorithm

To encrypt/decrypt a message e.g. letter 'W'		
ASCII value for 'W' = 119		
Two prime numbers are required i.e. P & Q	P = 29 (Assumption)	Q = 31 (Assumption)
N = p*q N = 29*31 = 899		
T = (p-1)*(q-1) T = (29-1)*(31-1) = 840		
Calculate e	e must be relatively prime to T	e.g. 11
Calculate d	$d * e = 1 \pmod T$ i.e. $(d * e) / t$ must give remainder of 1	Assuming d = 611 $(611 * 11) / 840 = 8 \text{ Rem } 1$ So 611 works
So P=29, Q = 31, N= 899, T=840, e=11, d = 611.		

Encrypting the Message: To encrypt the message, Private Key N and e are required

$$C = M^e \pmod N$$

$$C = \text{Cypher-Text} = 119^{11} \pmod 899 = \mathbf{595}$$

(This can be sent over to the server as shown above)

Decrypting the Message: In order to decrypt the message, Private Key N and d are required

$$M = C^d \bmod N$$

$$M = \text{Plain-Text} = 595^{611} \bmod 899 = \mathbf{119}$$

(119 represent letter 'M' i.e. Original Message)

CHAPTER THREE

QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY

Since the 1910s, one time pad (OTP) cryptosystems have been in use. The crypto-key length of OTP is the same as the length of the plain text. If the key is never reused, truly random, and kept secret, the OTP can be proven to be unbreakable. But the difficulty of securing the sharing key has prevented it from becoming practical. Quantum Cryptography or Quantum key distribution (QKD) is a new innovative technology that allows a more practical implementation of the classic OTP. This is because Quantum Cryptography enables two distant to generate a secret key that has guaranteed privacy due to the use of quantum physics. The secret key when it is used in an OTP cryptosystem provides perfect security.

Quantum Cryptography or Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) solves the key distribution problem by allowing the exchange of a cryptographic key between two remote parties with absolute security, guaranteed by the laws of quantum physics (Elboukhari, Azizi and Azizi, 2010). Quantum key distribution (QKD) uses individual photons for the exchange of cryptographic key between the sender and the receiver.

Each photon represents a single bit of data. The value of the bit, a 1 or a 0, is determined by states of the photon such as polarization or spin. With this method, one party can send a cryptographic key encoded with photons to another party. The unique properties of photons as quantum objects are such that any attempt to measure or to decipher the message will change the photons' state. This uncertainty ensures that the message will be destroyed or altered, making it easy for both the sender and receiver to detect that the message has been compromised. Thus, QKD doesn't rely on preventing interception or decryption, but rather on detecting eavesdropping and self-destructing the message as a result

To fully understand quantum cryptography theory, there is a need to clearly explain the concept of quantum computing, entanglement and superposition.

3.1 Quantum Computing

Quantum computation is performed in a quantum computer or processor, which is a processor that makes use of quantum mechanical phenomena, such as quantum superposition and quantum entanglement. Modern computers store data using a binary format called a "bit" in which a "1" or a "0" can be stored. The computations in modern computers typically work in a bit by bit fashion. Quantum computers store data using a quantum superposition of multiple states.

These multiple valued states are stored in "*quantum bits*" or "*qubits*." Depending on the quantum design, each qubit can store a set number values simultaneously (Jones 2009). This allows the computation of numbers to be several orders of magnitude faster than traditional transistor processors.

It is impossible to obtain information about a physical system without disturbing it in a random, uncontrollable way. This fundamental quantum-mechanical law guarantees the security of

Quantum Key Encryption (QKE) protocols by enabling the communicating parties to put an upper bound on how much an eavesdropper can know about the key.

Fig10: The Bloch sphere is a representation of a qubit, the fundamental building block of quantum computers.

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle,$$

$$|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$$

$$\alpha = \cos \frac{\theta}{2},$$

$$\beta = e^{i\phi} \sin \frac{\theta}{2},$$

The state space has two local degrees of freedom, which can be represented by the two angles ϕ and θ .

Where $e^{i\phi}$ is the significant relative space and

$$|\psi\rangle = \text{a pure qubit state}$$

3.1.1 Quantum Superposition

Superposition is the ability of a quantum system to be in multiple states at the same time until it is measured. The principle of quantum superposition states that if a physical system may be in one of many configurations or arrangements of particles or fields, then the most general state is a combination of all of these possibilities, where the amount in each configuration is specified by a complex number.

For example, if there are two configurations labelled by 0 and 1, the most general state would be:

$$c_0 | 0 \rangle + c_1 | 1 \rangle$$

Where the coefficients c_0 and c_1 are complex numbers describing how much goes into each configuration. Consider state vectors f_1 , f_2 and f_3 each solve the linear equation on ψ , then $\psi = (c_1 f_1 + c_2 f_2 + c_3 f_3)$ would also be a solution, in which each c is a *coefficient*.

Electrons possess a quantum feature called spin, a type of intrinsic angular momentum. In the presence of a magnetic field, the electron may exist in two possible spin states, usually referred to as spin up and spin down. Each electron, until it is measured, will have a finite chance of being in either state. Only when measured is it observed to be in a specific spin state.

For example, consider an electron with two possible configurations, up and down. This describes the physical system of a qubit.

$$c_1 |\uparrow\rangle + c_2 |\downarrow\rangle$$

$$p_{\text{up}} = |c_1|^2$$

$$p_{\text{down}} = |c_2|^2$$

$$p_{\text{up or down}} = p_{\text{up}} + p_{\text{down}} = 1$$

In reality, superposition can never actually be observed, all we can see is the consequences of their existence, after individual waves of a superposition interfere with each other. Thus, we can never observe an atom in its indeterminate state, or being in two places at once, only the resulting consequences, and physical reality is not determined until the act of measurement takes place and “solidifies” the situation into one state or another.

3.1.2 Quantum Entanglement

Quantum entanglement is one of the delightfully bizarre phenomena that underpins quantum computing. The basic idea behind it is that two particles can be linked to each other over any distance, even if that distance is the diameter of the universe. The effect happens instantaneously, but without going faster than the speed of light. It is the way that particles of energy/matter can become correlated to predictably interact with each other regardless of how far apart they are.

Particles, such as photons, electrons, or qubits that have interacted with each other retain a type of connection and can be entangled with each other in pairs, in the process known as

correlation. Knowing the spin state of one entangled particle, whether the direction of the spin is up or down, allows one to know that the spin of its mate is in the opposite direction. Even more amazing is the knowledge that, due to the phenomenon of *superposition*, the measured particle has no single spin direction before being measured, but is simultaneously in both a spin-up and spin-down state.

Fig11: Two particles exhibiting the Quantum Entanglement characteristics

The spin state of the particle being measured is decided at the time of measurement and communicated to the correlated particle, which simultaneously assumes the opposite spin direction to that of the measured particle. Quantum entanglement allows qubits that are separated by incredible distances to interact with each other immediately, in a communication that is not limited to the speed of light. No matter how great the distance between the correlated particles, they will remain entangled as long as they are isolated.

3.2 Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Protocol

A quantum (cryptographic) protocol is a data communications procedure that use quantum development designed to make secure communications. The foundation of quantum cryptography lies in the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, which states that certain pairs of physical properties are related in such a way that measuring one property prevents the observer from simultaneously knowing the value of the other.

The key is the main section of cryptography and should be sent in a much secured way. Huge cryptography has a different way of providing the key to the receiver, however quantum key distribution mechanism uses photons to provide a key unique to each transmitted information.

One of the important problems identified is using large cryptography is how to send or communicate data with photons. This matter can be easily set by offering the move of every photon as 0 or 1. The figure below will explain how to deliver details using photons

SPIN	Horizontal Spin (-)	Vertical Spin (l)	Left Diagonal Spin (\)	Right Diagonal Spin (/)
VALUE	0	1	0	1

Table 1: Relationship between photon spin and the encryption value.

Considering the sample polarisation and spin below

Polarization	x	+	+	x	+	+	+	x	x	x	+	+	x	x	+	x
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Spin	\	/	-	-		\	-	/	/	-		-		\	/	/
Value	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1

Table 2: Relationship between Polarization, spin and the assigned values

Polarization methods x = diagonal basis + = Rectilinear basis

The receiver is able to get the move of photon after polarization using four sensors (horizontal, directly, right tilted, staying diagonal). The key in binary structure is: **0101100110101011 (i.e. 22959)**.

To detect the eavesdrop polarization of the photon is to be measured. The key concept is that it is impossible to measure the polarization of the photon without destroying it. So if the photon breaker intercepts the signal, there will be need to send a new photons to the receiver so that the presence might not be detected. However, errors will be inevitably introduced, since the state and polarization were not known. So sender and receiver can check for errors by revealing a random subset of their generated sequence and comparing it publicly. If they are not satisfied with the error rate, they can set up a different channel.

3.3 Applications of Quantum Cryptography

During the last few years, progress has been made on formidable advances in digital and mobile communication technologies such as cordless and cellular telephones, personal communication systems, Internet connection expansion, etc. The vast majority of digital information used in all these applications is stored and also processed within a computer system, and then transferred between computers via fibre optic, satellite systems, and/or Internet.

In all those new scenarios, secure information transmission and storage has a paramount importance in the international information infrastructure, especially, for supporting electronic commerce and other security related services.

Under such a dynamic scenario, some of the most popular applications in the domain of information security include:

3.3.1 Ultra-Secure Voting

With political upheaval and accusations of voter fraud rampant in developed and developing countries alike, it's clear that making the voting process more secure is a necessity. Since 2007, Switzerland has been using quantum cryptography to conduct secure online voting in federal and regional elections.

In Geneva, votes are encrypted at a central vote-counting station. Then the results are transmitted over a dedicated optical fibre line to a remote data storage facility. The voting results are secured via quantum cryptography, and the most vulnerable part of the data transaction when the vote moves from counting station to central repository is uninterrupted

3.3.2 Secure Outbound Communications with Space

Secure communications with satellites and astronauts is an increasing concern, and a company called Quintessence Labs is working on a project for NASA that will ensure secure communications from Earth with satellites and astronauts. The goal of the project is to achieve a protocol which guarantees the security of communications regardless of the technology or intelligence to which an adversary has access. It also includes a mandate to secure both information “at rest” and in transit. This would ultimately increase the safety of astronauts in space

3.3.3 Quantum Internet

Today’s internet is relatively fast, but its security is paltry compared to quantum-encrypted transmissions. Quantum encryption would greatly slow down the internet. In the future, however, it’s possible that we could switch effortlessly between “regular” and “quantum encrypted” internet, so that our most sensitive transmissions would be passed along in an ultra-secure manner. This would achieve the ideal of a simultaneously fast and secure internet.

Other areas under consideration are:

- Secure e-mail
- Smatter Power Grid
- Client-Server transactions
- Virtual Private Networks
- E-cash / Electronic Financial transactions
- Grid Computing etc.

CONCLUSION

There has been a historical pattern that shows the country with the strongest encryption has been a leader in military power, healthcare, finance and other major areas of life. By studying cryptography and encryption, a country could strengthen its defences and have the necessary means to survive in a hostile world. An understanding of encryption can also help individuals with securing private data and information.

Even though it is severely unethical, our communication with one another is constantly being monitored. Those who monitor our communication can include governments, internet service providers, hackers, identity thieves, and more. By learning to use cryptography for secure communication, we can safe guard ourselves from being compromised by those who could steal our information.

Cryptography is illegal in many countries because the local government wishes to be able to read any transmission sent. Many people speculate that the United States does not need these laws because the NSA has developed methods of cryptanalysis that break all encryption methods currently known.

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